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Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in statistics. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Data . population and Frequency distribution

Statistical methods are concerned with scientific methods for collecting, organizing, summarizing, presenting and analyzing data as well as with drawing valid conclusions and making reasonable decision on the basis of such analysis.

Data: Data are the facts and figures that are collected, analyzed and summarized for presentation and interpretation (facts).

Qualitative data: Qualitative data are concerned with the presence or absence of certain characteristics in a set of objects or individuals.

Ex: If we have a record of baby births we may be concerned with only whether the baby is male or not and count the number of male babies.

Quantitative data: Quantitative data are concerned with the actual magnitude (numerical value) of some character for each of the individuals.

2	52-55
8	55-60
15	60-65
25	65-70
30	70-75

Ex: The height of a person, the number of children in a family constitute quantitative data.

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Population and Sample

Population: A population is the set of all elements of interest to a particular study. In statistical population, it also means a group of individuals.

Sample: A sample is a representative part of the population.

It is often impractical or even impossible to study the entire universe. This is why decisions about a population are usually drawn on the basis of a sample.

↓

Frequency Distribution:

Definition: To summarize large number of raw data, it is often useful to distribute the data into classes or categories and to determine the number of individuals in each class, called the class frequency. A tabular arrangement of data by classes together with the corresponding class frequencies is called a frequency distribution.

The following table is a frequency distribution of heights (recorded to the nearest inch) of 100 male students at city university.

Height (inch)	Number of Student (f)
60-62	5
63-65	18
66-68	42
69-71	27
72-74	8

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Here, $60-62$ → class interval (ক্লাস ব্যবধি)
 Lower class limit (LCL) = 60
 Upper class limit (UCL) = 62
 Sub interval/width = 2

60	61	62	63	64
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Range = Maximum - Minimum = $74 - 60 = 14$

class mark / Mid point = $\frac{UCL + LCL}{2}$

Frequency distribution

Ungrouped or Discrete frequency distribution

Grouped or Continuous frequency distribution

Ungrouped frequency distribution: when the number of values of variable is small, then we construct an ungrouped frequency distribution.

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As for example, let us assume that 20 families were surveyed to find out how many children they had. The raw data obtained from the survey is,

0, 2, 3, 1, 3, 4, 2, 0, 3, 4, 2, 2, 1, 0, 4, 1, 2, 2, 3

Number of children (X)	Frequency
0	3
1	4
2	6
3	4
4	3
Total	20

Grouped frequency distribution: If the data is very large, it becomes necessary to condense the data into a suitable number of groups or classes of variable values and then assigning the combined frequencies of these values to their respective classes.

For example, 100 employees were surveyed in a factory to find out their ages. The youngest person was 20 years old and the oldest was 49 years old.

The frequency distribution is given below:

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Age group	Frequency (F)
20 to less than 25	5
25 to less than 30	15
30 to less than 35	25
35 to less than 40	30
40 to less than 45	15
45 to less than 50	10
Total	100

General rules for forming a frequency distribution:

- (i) To determine the largest and smallest numbers in the raw data and then find the range.
- (ii) The classes should be clearly defined and each of the observation should be included in only one these class intervals.
- (iii) The number of classes should neither be too large nor too small.
- (iv) All intervals should be of the same width.

$$\text{width} = \frac{\text{Range}}{\text{Number of classes}}$$

Exc: The width of intervals to be assigned to the data is to be determined by the following formula:

$$\text{width} = \frac{\text{Range}}{1 + 3.322 \log N}$$

where, N is the number of observations.

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Exc: A sample of 30 persons showed their ages as follows
 construct a frequency distribution of os

20, 18, 25, 68, 23, 25, 16, 22, 29, 37, 55, 49, 42, 65, 37, 42, 63, 65,
 49, 42, 53, 48, 65, 72, 69, 57, 48, 39, 58, 67

Range = $72 - 16$
 $= 56$

width = $\frac{\text{Range}}{1 + 3.3222 \log N}$
 $= \frac{56}{1 + 3.3222 \log 30}$
 $= 9.98 \approx 10$

Class Interval	Tally marks	Frequency (f)
15 to less than 25		5
25 to less than 35		3
35 to < 45		5
45 to < 55		4
55 to < 65		3
65 to < 75		5
Total →		30

Exc: The weights of 40 students at city university are recorded to the nearest pound. Construct a frequency distribution.

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138 164 150 132 144 125 149 157
 168 126 138 176 163 156 154 169
 146 173 142 147 135 153 140 135
 161 145 135 142 156 158 145 128

Ans: Here, Range = 176 - 119 = 57

Width = $\frac{\text{Range}}{1 + 3.322 \cdot \log 40} = \frac{57}{1 + 3.322 \cdot \log 40} = 9.01 \sim 10$

Class interval	Tally marks	Frequency
118 to less than 128		4
128 to less than 138		5
138 to less than 148		5
148 to less than 158		5
158 to less than 168		4
168 to less than 178		4
Total		40

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Graphical presentation of data: The following are the main types of graphs and diagrams:

- (i) Line diagram
- (ii) Bar diagram
- (iii) Histogram
- (iv) Frequency polygon
- (v) Cumulative frequency polygon
- (vi) Pie-diagram.

Line diagram: If we are given the values of a variable at different points of time, the set of values is known as a time-series. The line diagram is used to represent time-series data. Line diagrams are particularly effective for business because we can show the change in a variable over time.

Exc: The following table shows the net sales of Apex Apparel from 1995 through 2000. Draw a line diagram.

	Amount in million taka					
Year	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000
Net Sales	500	520	490	530	550	575

Solve: The above data can be presented by the following line diagram.

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(288) Bar diagram is a bar diagram that is commonly used for presentation of qualitative or categorical data. Bars are simply thick vertical lines (bars) where the length of the lines corresponds to their numerical values. The width of the bar is not important but it should be uniform so as not to create confusion. The bars should be equally spaced.

Ex: Construct a bar diagram for the population of some selected countries in 1998 from the following.

Country	Bangladesh	Egypt	Indonesia	Pakistan	Turkey
Population (million)	113	56	187	123	59

Solve: The bar diagram of the above table is given below:

Figure: Bar diagram.

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Ex: Construct a bar diagram for the total expenditures (in taka) in taka of a family during 1995 to 1998 and also to

Year	Expenditures
1995	8000
1996	10,500
1997	12,500
1998	16,000

The bar diagram of above table is given below:

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Histogram: It is a two dimensional graphical presentation of data where class intervals are marked along the X-axis and the frequencies along the Y-axis according to suitable scale. A histogram is constructed from a frequency distribution of grouped data, where the height of the rectangle is proportion to the respective frequency and the width represent class intervals.

Exc: Construct a histogram using the following grouped frequency distribution of the ages of 30 persons.

Class interval	Frequency (f)
15-25	5
25-35	3
35-45	7
45-55	5
55-65	3
65-75	7

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Ex: Construct a histogram using the following table which shows the weekly wages (Taka) of 65 employees at a garment factory.

Wages	No of employees (f)
\$ 250-260	8
260-270	10
270-280	16
280-290	14
290-300	10
300-310	5
310-320	2

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Frequency polygon (৩২৩৩): A frequency polygon is a line chart of frequency distribution in which either the values of discrete variable or mid-point of class intervals are plotted against the frequencies and these plotted points are joined together by straight lines

The presentation involves presenting the mid values on the horizontal axis(x) and the frequencies on the vertical axis(y).

Exc: Construct a frequency polygon using the following grouped frequency distribution of the ages of 30 persons.

Class interval	Frequency (f)
15-25	5
25-35	3
35-45	7
45-55	5
55-65	3
65-75	7

Ans: The frequency polygon of the above table is given below.

Class interval	Frequency (f)	Mid-value
15-25	5	20
25-35	3	30
35-45	7	40
45-55	5	50
55-65	3	60
65-75	7	70

Class interval	Frequency (f)	Class interval
25-35	3	35-45
35-45	7	45-55
45-55	5	55-65
55-65	3	65-75
65-75	7	

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Construct a frequency polygon using the following table which shows the weekly wages of 65 employees at a garments factory.

Wages	No of employees (f)
\$ 250-260	8
260-270	10
270-280	16
280-290	14
290-300	10
300-310	5
310-320	2

Ans:

Class interval	Frequency (f)	Mid value
\$ 250-260	8	255
260-270	10	265
270-280	16	275
280-290	14	285
290-300	10	295
300-310	5	305

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Cumulative frequency polygon:

The total frequency of all values less than the upper class boundary of a given class interval is called the cumulative frequency upto and including that class interval. A table presenting such cumulative frequencies is called a cumulative frequency distribution. A graph showing the cumulative frequency less than any upper class boundary plotted against the upper class boundary is called a cumulative frequency polygon.

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Ques: The heights (recorded to the nearest inch) of 100 students at city university are given in the following table. Construct a cumulative frequency polygon.

Height (inch)	No of student (f)
60-62	5
63-65	18
66-68	42
69-71	27
72-74	8

Ans:

Height (inch)	No of student (f)	C.f
60-62	5	5
63-65	18	23
66-68	42	65
69-71	27	92
72-74	8	100

The cumulative frequency of the above table is given below:

A cumulative frequency polygon is a line graph that represents the cumulative frequency of a data set. It is constructed by plotting the upper class boundary of each class against its cumulative frequency and joining the points by straight lines. The resulting polygon is called a cumulative frequency polygon.

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Ex: Following table shows the weekly wages of 65 employees at a garment factory. Construct a cumulative frequency polygon.

Wages (\$)	No of employees (f)	C.f
250-260	8	8
260-270	10	18
270-280	16	34
280-290	14	48
290-300	10	58
300-310	5	63
310-320	2	65

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The following is an example of pie chart showing show-rizes of 100 people.

Exc: The pie-chart shown in following represents the numbers of cattle, sheep and goats on a firm.

Ques: (i) Find the angles which represents the numbers of goats on the firm

- (ii) There are 28 Cattle on the firm.
- (iii) Find the number of goats on the firm.
- (iv) Find the total numbers of cattle, sheep and goat.

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Solve:

(i) The angle representing the number of goats

$$= 360^\circ - (96^\circ + 120^\circ)$$

(ii) Number of goats = $\frac{28}{96} \times 144 = 42$

(iii) Number of total goats, sheep and cattle = $\frac{28}{96} \times 360$

(iv) Number of sheep = $\frac{28}{96} \times 120$

Exc: The proportion of drinks sold at the refreshment tent at a summer fair are represented by the pie-chart in figure. The number of coffees sold was 135

(i) Calculate the total number of drinks sold.

(ii) Calculate the number of orange juice drinks sold.

(iii) Calculate the number of lemonade drinks sold.

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Measures of central tendency: Measures of central tendency is a value that is typical or representative, of a set of data. Several types of measures can be defined, they are-

- (i) Mean
 - Arithmetic Mean $\bar{x} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$
 - Geometric Mean $\bar{x} = \sqrt[n]{x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_n}$
 - Harmonic Mean $\bar{x} = \frac{n}{\frac{1}{x_1} + \frac{1}{x_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{x_n}}$

(ii) Median

(iii) Mode.

Arithmetic Mean: The arithmetic mean of a set of numbers $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ is denoted by \bar{x} and is defined by

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_n}{n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

If the numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n occur f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n times respectively, the arithmetic mean is

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x_1 f_1 + x_2 f_2 + \dots + x_n f_n}{f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i}$$

The harmonic mean of a set of numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is the reciprocal of the arithmetic mean of the reciprocals of the numbers.

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The Geometric Mean of the Geometric mean of a set of N positive numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N is the N th root of the product of the numbers.

$$GM = \sqrt[N]{x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_N} = (x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_N)^{\frac{1}{N}} \quad (i)$$

Exc: $2, 4, 8 \rightarrow GM = \sqrt[3]{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 8}$
 $= 3\sqrt[3]{64} = 4$

If the numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N occurs with frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N where $N = f_1 + f_2 + f_3 + \dots + f_N$

then $GM = \sqrt[N]{x_1^{f_1} \cdot x_2^{f_2} \cdot \dots \cdot x_N^{f_N}}$

Exc: $\frac{2^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 8^3 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 9^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 6^3 \cdot 3^3}{1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1} = \bar{x}$

$$GM = \sqrt[11]{2^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 8^3 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 9^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 6^3 \cdot 3^3}$$

$$= \frac{2^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 8^3 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 9^3 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 6^3 \cdot 3^3}{11} = \bar{x}$$

Harmonic Mean: The harmonic mean of a set of N numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N is the reciprocal of the arithmetic mean of the reciprocals of the numbers.

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Find the harmonic mean for the following data

$$HM = \frac{N}{\sum \frac{1}{x_i}}$$

$$HM = \frac{N}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i}}$$

The harmonic mean for grouped data x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n respectively

$$\frac{1}{HM} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{f_1}{x_1} + \frac{f_2}{x_2} + \dots + \frac{f_n}{x_n} \right)$$

Calculate the harmonic mean for the following data

(x) number of children	(f) no of children
2	20
3	30
4	50
5	50
6	50

$$\frac{1}{HM} = \frac{1}{200} \left(\frac{20}{2} + \frac{30}{3} + \frac{50}{4} + \frac{50}{5} + \frac{50}{6} \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{200} (10 + 10 + 12.5 + 10 + 8.33)$$

$$= \frac{50.83}{200}$$

$$HM = \frac{200}{50.83} = 3.93$$

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*** Find the Harmonic mean of the following numbers.

3, 5, 6, 6, 7, 10, 12

Harmonic mean = $\frac{N}{\sum \frac{1}{x}}$

$\frac{7}{\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{12}}$

$\frac{7}{\left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{12}\right)} = \frac{1}{MH}$

*** Calculate the Harmonic mean of the following frequency distribution

No of children (x)	No of families (f)
1	5
2	30
3	20
4	25
5	20

Harmonic mean = $\frac{N}{\sum \frac{f}{x}}$

$= \frac{100}{5 + \frac{30}{2} + \frac{20}{3} + \frac{25}{4} + \frac{20}{5}}$
 $= \frac{100}{36.7}$

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Calculate the arithmetic mean and Geometric mean.

No. of children (x)	No. of families (f)
1	5
2	30
3	20
4	25
5	20

Arithmetic mean = $\frac{1 \cdot 5 + 2 \cdot 30 + 3 \cdot 20 + 4 \cdot 25 + 5 \cdot 20}{100} = \frac{325}{100} = 3.25$

Geometric mean = $\sqrt[100]{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5}$

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The following table gives the heights of 100 students of city university. Find Arithmetic mean and Harmonic mean and show that $AM \geq HM$

Height (inch)	Number of students	Mid value
60-62	5	61
62-64	18	63
64-66	42	65
66-68	20	67
68-70	8	69
70-72	7	71

Ans:

Arithmetic mean = $\frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$

Harmonic mean = $\frac{\sum f}{\sum \frac{f}{x}}$

AM \geq HM

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Median of a series of values are arranged in order of magnitudes, the median is the middle most or central value of the series.

2011-12 = 3K, 1-20
 3K 1+6 3x2k (17-26) + 1 = 3Kosibem 1+
 2, 5, 0, 9, 7, 11, 14, 18, 10

0, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 11, 18

Median = $\frac{5+7}{2} = 6$

In general, if we have a set of n observations, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n arranged in ascending order that is $x_1 \leq x_2 \leq x_3 \leq \dots \leq x_n$

Then the median is the value x_p if n is odd ($n = 2p - 1$) and the median is taken to be equal to $\frac{x_p + x_{p+1}}{2}$ if n is even, $n = 2p$

Ex: Ascending order,

	0	2	3	4	5	7	9	10	11	18
Median	$\frac{x_p + x_{p+1}}{2}$									
	5	7								
	$\frac{5+7}{2}$									
	6									

= 6 Ans.

$n = 2p - 1$
 $10 = 2p - 1$
 $\Rightarrow 2p = 10$
 $p = 5$

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steps to find grouped data (frequency distribution) is the
 last median is given by, $n/2$ position of observation

$$\text{Median} = L_1 + \frac{(n/2 - F_1)}{f} \times c$$

where, $L_1 = 8, 11, 10, 19, 7, 7, 2, 8, 5, 0$

L_1 = Lower class boundary of the median class.

n = Total frequency

F_1 = Sum of frequencies of all classes lower than the median class

class

f = Frequency of the median class

c = Size of the median class

Ex: $(10-15)$ size/width

Example:
 $n = 95$
 $n/2 = 47.5$
 47.5 is between 45 and 52

C	f	C.f
5-10	5	5
10-15	12	17
15-20	20	37
20-25	8	45
25-30	7	52

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Calculate Median, $L_1 = 15$, $F_1 = 17$, $f_m = 20$, $e = 5$

$\therefore \text{Median} = 15 + \frac{5 \times \frac{50}{20}}{20} = 15 + \frac{12.5}{20} = 15 + 0.625 = 15.625$

*** The following table shows the distribution of heights of randomly selected 100 students of city university. Calculate the median

Height (inch)	Frequency (f)	Cumulative Frequency
60-62	5	5
62-64	18	23
64-66	42	65
66-68	20	85
68-70	8	93
70-72	7	100

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Here,

$$L_1 = 64$$

$$n = 100$$

$$f_1 = 23$$

$$f_m = 42$$

$$c = 2$$

$$\therefore \text{Median} = 64 + \frac{\frac{100}{2} - 23}{42 + 23} \times 2$$

$$= 64 + \frac{50 - 23}{65} \times 2$$

$$= 64 + \frac{54}{65}$$

Height (inches)	Frequency
60-62	5
62-64	18
64-66	23
66-68	38
68-70	8
70-72	100

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Mode: The mode is the value of the variable that occurs most frequently. i.e. for which the frequency is maximum. The mode of a frequency distribution can be obtained by the formula

$$\text{Mode} = L_1 + \left(\frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2} \right) \times c$$

where, L_1 = lower class boundary of the modal class

c = size of the modal class interval

Δ_1 = Excess of modal frequency over frequency of next lower class.

Δ_2 = Excess of modal frequency over frequency of the next higher class.

Exc: The following table shows the distribution of heights of randomly selected.

60-62	5
62-64	18
64-66	42
66-68	20
68-70	8
70-72	7

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Here

$$L_1 = 64$$

$$\Delta_1 = 42 - 18 = 24$$

$$\Delta_2 = 42 - 20 = 22$$

$$C = 2$$

$$\text{Mode} = 64 + \frac{24}{24 + 22} \times 2 = 65.09$$

$$= 64 + \frac{48}{46}$$

$$= 65.04 \text{ Ans.}$$

Median → **মধ্যক**
 Model → **প্রকুরক**

2	62-62
81	62-62
47	62-62
50	62-62
8	62-62
4	62-62

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Measures of dispersion

Mean deviation: The mean deviation of a set of N numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N is denoted by M.D and defined by

$$M.D = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_i - \bar{x}|$$

where, \bar{x} = Mean of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N

The mean deviation of a grouped data x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N with frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N is given by

$$M.D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f_i |x_i - \bar{x}|}{N}$$

where, $N = \sum f_i$

Ex: Calculate the mean deviation of the following values.

10, 4, 5, 7, 2, 14, 3, 6, 20, -8

Solⁿ:

x_i	10	4	5	7	2	14	3	6	20	-8
\bar{x}	$\frac{\sum x_i}{N} = \frac{63}{10} = 6.3$									
$ x_i - \bar{x} $	3.7	2.3	1.3	0.7	4.3	7.7	0.3	3	13.7	14.3

$$\therefore M.D = \frac{0.7 + 2.3 + \dots + 14.3}{10}$$

$$= \frac{51.6}{10} = 5.16 \text{ Ans.}$$

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*** Calculate the mean deviation of the following frequency distribution

x_i	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95
f_i	4	9	24	30	62	28	23	12	6	2

Ans:

x_i	f_i	$f_i x_i$	$ x_i - \bar{x} $	$f_i x_i - \bar{x} $
50	4	200	19.67	78.68
55	9	495	14.67	132.03
60	24	1440	9.67	232.08
65	30	1950	4.67	140.1
70	62	4340	0.33	20.46
75	28	2100	5.33	149.24
80	23	1840	10.33	237.59
85	12	1020	15.33	183.96
90	6	540	20.33	121.98
95	2	190	25.33	50.66

$\sum f_i = 200$
 $\sum f_i x_i = 13935$

$\sum f_i (x_i - \bar{x}) = 1346.78$

$\therefore M.D = \frac{\sum f_i (x_i - \bar{x})}{N} = \frac{1346.78}{200} = 6.73$

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The following are the steps to find the standard deviation:

Standard deviation:
 The standard deviation of a set of N numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N is denoted by S and is defined by

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

If x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N occurs with frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N respectively, the standard deviation is given by

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	$ x_i - \bar{x} $	N	f_i	$(x_i - \bar{x}) f_i$
100	10	100	1	100
400	20	400	10	4000

Exc: Find the standard deviation of the following set of numbers

- ① 12, 6, 7, 3, 15, 10, 18, 5
- ② 9, 3, 8, 7, 9, 8, 19, 18

x_i	\bar{x}	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$
12	9.34	7.07
6		11.15
7		5.47
3		40.1
15		32.0
10		9.9
18		74.99
5		18.83
8		1.79
		$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{191.83}{9}}$$

$$= \sqrt{21.31}$$

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x_i	$\sum x_i$	$(x_i - \bar{x})$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$
9		1.265	
3		50.76	
8	$\sum x_i$	4.51	
7	$= \frac{81}{8}$	89.76	
9	$= 10.125$	11.26	
8		4.51	
19		78.76	
18		62.01	
		$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$	

$(x_i - \bar{x})$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$	N	$\frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}$
1.265	1.600225	212.83	180	1.1824
50.76	2576.5776			
4.51	20.3401			
89.76	8056.8176			
11.26	126.7776			
4.51	20.3401			
78.76	6203.1296			
62.01	3845.2401			
		$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$		

$$= \sqrt{\frac{212.83}{8}}$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{26.60375}{1}}$$

$$= 5.15$$

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Find the standard deviation of the height of the 100 students at city university whose grouped data is given below.

Height (inch)	No. of students
60-62	5
63-65	18
66-68	42
69-71	27
72-74	8
	100

Ans:

x_i	f_i	$f_i x_i$	$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum f_i x_i}{\sum f_i}$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	$f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2$
61	5	305	$\bar{x} = \frac{6745}{100} = 67.45$	42.25	211.25
64	18	1152		11.90	214.2
67	42	2814		6.50	175.5
70	27	1890		5.55	44.4
73	8	584			
	100				

$$\frac{\sum f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N} = \frac{653.75}{100} = 6.5375$$

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{653.75}{100}}$$

$$= \sqrt{6.5375} = 2.55 \text{ Ans.}$$

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Moments of skewness and kurtosis: If x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N are the

N values, then r -th moment is defined by

$$x^r = \frac{x_1^r + x_2^r + \dots + x_N^r}{N}$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^r}{N}$$

The r -th moment about the mean \bar{x} is defined as

$$m_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^r}{N}$$

The r -th moment about any origin A is defined as

$$m'_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - A)^r}{N}$$

Moments of grouped data: If x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N occur with frequencies f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N respectively, then

$$x^r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f_i x_i^r}{N}$$

$$m_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^r}{N}$$

x_i	f_i	$(x_i - \bar{x})^r$	$f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^r$
10	10		
8	10		
7	10		
6	10		
5	10		
4	10		
3	10		
2	10		
1	10		
0	10		
-1	10		
-2	10		
-3	10		
-4	10		
-5	10		
-6	10		
-7	10		
-8	10		
-9	10		
-10	10		
Total	100		

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Exc: Find the (a) second (b) fourth moments of the set

2, 3, 7, 8, 10

Ans:

$$\bar{x}^2 = \frac{2^2 + 3^2 + 7^2 + 8^2 + 10^2}{5} = \frac{16594}{5} = 3318.8$$

The 2-th moment about the mean is

$$= \frac{5(\bar{x}^2 - \bar{x}^2)}{5} = 5 \cdot 2 = 10$$

The 4-th moment about the mean is

$$\bar{x}^4 = \frac{2^4 + 3^4 + 7^4 + 8^4 + 10^4}{5} = \frac{16594}{5} = 3318.8$$

Moments of grouped data are calculated as follows

$$= 3318.8$$

Exc: Find the (a) second (b) fourth moment about the mean for the set of numbers 2, 3, 7, 8, 10

x_i	\bar{x}	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^4$	$\therefore m_2 = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{5}$
2		16	256	5
3		9	81	46
7		1	1	5
8		4	16	9.2
10		16	256	5
	$\frac{\sum x_i}{N} = \frac{30}{5}$	$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = 46$	$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^4 = 610$	$m_4 = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^4}{5} = \frac{610}{5}$

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Ex: Find the (a) third (b) fourth moments about the origin for the set of numbers 2, 3, 7, 8, 10

x_i	$(x_i - 4)^3$	$(x_i - 4)^4$
2	-8	16
3	-1	1
7	27	81
8	64	256
10	216	1296

$$\sum (x_i - 4)^3 = 298$$

$$\sum (x_i - 4)^4 = 1650$$

$$\therefore m'_3 = \frac{\sum (x_i - 4)^3}{5} = \frac{298}{5} = 59.6$$

$$m'_4 = \frac{\sum (x_i - 4)^4}{5} = \frac{1650}{5} = 330$$

Skewness: skewness is the degree of asymmetry or departure for symmetry of a distribution.

If the frequency polygon of a distribution has a longer tail to the right of the central symmetry maximum than to left, the distribution is said to be skewed to the right or to have positive skewness.

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If the frequency polygon of a distribution has a longer tail to the left of the central maximum than to right. The distribution is said to be skewed to the left or to the negative skewness.

$$\text{Skewness} = \frac{\text{Mean} - \text{Mode}}{\sigma}$$

Standard deviation

$$\text{Skewness} = \frac{\text{Mean} - \text{Median}}{\sigma}$$

Standard deviation

Kurtosis: Kurtosis is the degree of peakness of frequency polygon.

A frequency polygon having a relatively high peak is called leptokurtic

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A frequency polygon having a relatively flat-topped is called **Platykurtic**.

A frequency polygon which is not very peaked or very flat-topped, is called **mesokurtic**.

Probabability: The probability of an event is the measure of the chance that the event will occur as a result of an experiment.

$$\text{Probability} = \frac{\text{The number of ways an event can occur}}{\text{Total number of possible outcomes}}$$

Probability scale $\neq 0$ to 1

Mutually exclusive event: Mutually exclusive events are sets of events or outcomes for which the happening of one of them means that none of the others can happen.

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Example: when rolling a dice the outcomes are mutually exclusive. since when one number comes to the top, it must mean that none of the others can come to the top.

Independent events: Two or more events or outcomes are independent if the happening of one of them has no effect on the other.

Example: when two dice are rolled, there are two independent outcomes, since the numbers showing on one does not influence the numbers on the other.

Conditional probability: If E_1 and E_2 are two events, the probability that E_2 occurs given that E_1 has occurred is denoted.

$$P(E_2/E_1) \text{ or } P(E_2 \text{ given } E_1)$$

and is called the conditional probability of E_2 given that E_1 has occurred

If the occurrence or non occurrence of E_1 does not affect the probability of occurrence of E_2 then

$$P(E_2/E_1) = P(E_2)$$

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and we say that E_1 and E_2 are independent events. Otherwise, they are called dependent events.

If we denote $E_1 E_2$ the event that both E_1 and E_2 occur called compound event, then

$$P(E_1, E_2) = P(E_1) \cdot P(E_2|E_1)$$

For independent events:

$$P(E_1 E_2) = P(E_1) \cdot P(E_2)$$

Ex: A single 6 sided die is rolled what is the probability of

- (i) Each outcome (ii) Rolling an even number (iii) rolling an odd number

Odd = বিজড়, Even = জড়

Ans:

(1) $P(\text{Each outcome}) = \frac{1}{6}$

(2) $P(\text{an even number}) = \frac{3}{6} = \frac{1}{2}$

(3) $P(\text{an odd number}) = \frac{3}{6} = \frac{1}{2}$

Ex: A box contains 8 red, 3 white and 9 blue balls. If three balls are drawn and random, determine the probability that

- (a) All three are red
- (b) All three are white
- (c) At least 1 is white
- (d) 2 are red and one is white

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Ans: $P_r(\text{three are red}) = \frac{\binom{8}{2}}{\binom{20}{3}} = \frac{28}{1140} = \frac{7}{285}$

(b) $P_r(\text{three are white}) = \frac{\binom{3}{3}}{\binom{20}{3}} = \frac{1}{1140}$

(c) $P_r(\text{None in white}) = \frac{\binom{17}{3}}{\binom{20}{3}} = \frac{680}{1140} = \frac{34}{57}$

$P_r(\text{at least one in white}) = 1 - \frac{34}{57} = \frac{23}{57}$

(d) $P_r(\text{2 are red and one is white}) = \frac{\binom{8}{2} \binom{3}{1}}{\binom{20}{3}}$

(e) $P_r(1 \text{ in each colour}) = \frac{\binom{8}{1} \binom{3}{1} \binom{9}{1}}{\binom{20}{3}}$

Exc. A box contains 8 white and 9 blue balls. Determine the probability that...

Exc. Five cards are drawn from a pack of 52 well-shuffled cards. Find the probability that

(a) 4 are aces

(b) 4 are aces and 1 is king

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(c) 3 ace 10's and 2 ace jacks
 (d) 6 9's 10, jack, queen and king are obtained in any order

Ex: The number of ways to draw a deck pack of 52 cards is $\binom{52}{5}$
 (e) at least one ace is obtained

Ans: (a)
$$P_r(4 \text{ ace}) = \frac{\binom{4}{4} \binom{48}{1}}{\binom{52}{5}} = \frac{48}{2598960}$$

(b)
$$P_r(4 \text{ ace and 1 in king}) = \frac{\binom{4}{4} \binom{1}{1}}{\binom{52}{5}} = \frac{1}{2598960}$$

(c)
$$P_r(3 \text{ ace 10's and 2 ace jacks}) = \frac{\binom{4}{3} \binom{4}{2}}{\binom{52}{5}} = \frac{24}{2598960}$$

(d)
$$P_r(6 \text{ 9's 10's jack, queen and king}) = \frac{\binom{4}{1} \binom{4}{1} \binom{4}{1} \binom{4}{1} \binom{4}{1}}{\binom{52}{5}} = \frac{1024}{2598960} = \frac{64}{162435}$$

(e)
$$P_r(\text{No. ace is obtained}) = \frac{\binom{48}{5}}{\binom{52}{5}} = \frac{1712304}{2598960} = .65$$

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Pr (at least one is ace) = $1 - \frac{48}{52}$

Pr (at least one is king) = $1 - \frac{48}{52}$

Exc: Three cards are drawn from a deck/pack of 52 cards.
 Find the probability that.

(a) Two are jacks and one is king

(b) all cards are of one suit

(c) At least two aces are drawn

Ans: (a) $P = \frac{\binom{4}{2} \binom{4}{1}}{\binom{52}{3}} = \frac{6 \times 4}{22100} = \frac{24}{22100}$

(b) $P = \frac{\binom{13}{3}}{\binom{52}{3}} = \frac{286}{22100} = \frac{13}{1050}$

(c) $P = \frac{\binom{4}{2} \binom{48}{1} + \binom{4}{1} \binom{48}{2}}{\binom{52}{3}} = \frac{6 \times 48 + 4 \times 1128}{22100} = \frac{5280}{22100} = \frac{264}{1105}$

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*** Tree Diagram: Tree diagrams are drawn to find and display all possible results when several outcomes are being combined.

Example: when 3 coins are tossed all possible results can be found and displayed by using a tree diagram.

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Ex: A box contains eight eggs. Five of the eggs are perfect and three are cracked (cr). A farmer chooses two eggs at random from the box.

Example: when a checker is used to check the eggs, the following tree diagram is used.

(a) Write the four remaining probabilities on the tree diagram.

(b) Calculate the probability that

- (i) Both eggs will be perfect
- (ii) At least one of the two eggs will be cracked.

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(b)

P_0 (Both eggs are perfect) = $\frac{5}{8} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{5}{16}$ Ans.

P_0 (Both eggs are cracked) = $\frac{3}{8} \times \frac{2}{7}$

(c) P_0 (at least one of the two eggs will be cracked)

= $(\frac{5}{8} \times \frac{3}{7}) + (\frac{3}{8} \times \frac{5}{7}) + (\frac{3}{8} \times \frac{2}{7})$

= $\frac{15}{56} + \frac{15}{56} + \frac{2}{28}$

= $\frac{36}{56} = \frac{9}{14}$ Ans.

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Probability distribution

The Binomial distribution: If p is the probability that an event will happen in any single trial (Probability of a success) and $q = 1-p$ is the probability that it will fail to happen in any single trial (Probability of a failure), then the probability that the event will happen exactly x times in N trials, is given by

$$P(x) = \binom{N}{x} p^x q^{N-x}$$

where, $x = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$

The above distribution is called Binomial distribution.

Find the probability that in five tosses of a fair die, a 3 appears (ছয়টি ফেলার ৩ আসা)

- (a) at no time
- (b) Once
- (c) Twice
- (d) Three times
- (e) Four times.

Ans.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(3 \text{ appears zero time}) &= \binom{5}{0} \left(\frac{1}{6}\right)^0 \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^{5-0} \\
 &= 1 \cdot 1 \cdot \frac{3125}{7776} \\
 &= \frac{3125}{7776}
 \end{aligned}$$

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Ex. Find the probability that in a family of 4 children there will be

(a) At least 1 boy $\frac{1}{2^4} = \frac{1}{16} = Y$

(b) At least 1 boy and 1 girl

Ans: $P_r(1 \text{ boy}) = \binom{4}{1} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^1 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 = \frac{1}{4}$

$P_r(2 \text{ boys}) = \binom{4}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2$

$P_r(3 \text{ boys}) = \binom{4}{3} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^1 = \frac{1}{4}$

$P_r(4 \text{ boys}) = \binom{4}{4} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^0 = \frac{1}{16}$

$\therefore P_r(\text{at least 1 boy}) = \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{8} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{16}\right) = \frac{15}{16}$ Ans.

Another method,

$P_r(\text{No boy}) = \binom{4}{0} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^0 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^4 = \frac{1}{16}$

$P_r(\text{at least 1 boy}) = 1 - \frac{1}{16} = \frac{15}{16}$ Ans

(b) $P_r(\text{No boy}) = \binom{4}{0} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^0 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^4 = \frac{1}{16}$

$P_r(\text{No girl}) = \binom{4}{0} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^0 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^4 = \frac{1}{16}$

$P_r(\text{At least 1 boy and 1 girl}) = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{16}\right)$

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The Normal distribution: The normal distribution is defined by the equation.

$$Y = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

where, $\mu = \text{Mean}$
 $\sigma = \text{Standard deviation}$
 $\pi = 3.14$
 $e = 2.71828$

The poisson distribution: The poisson distribution is given by

$$P(x) = \frac{\lambda^x e^{-\lambda}}{x!}$$

where $\lambda = 2.71828$ and λ is a given constant.

Regression and correlation

Regression: The regression analysis is a technique of analyzing or studying the dependence of one variable on one or more variables.

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For regression analysis we express the relation between the independent and independent variables by means of an equation which is known as regression

The regression equation is given by $y = a + bx$

where, $a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x}$

$$b = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{n (\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2}$$

Ex: The following sample observations were obtained in a study of cost of advertisement and the profit earned (amount in lakh taka)

Cost of advertisement (x)	4	5	3	6	10
Profit earned (y)	5	6	5	7	7

- (a) Determine the regression equation.
 (b) Determine the profit expected to the earned when cost of advertisement is taka 9 Lakh

Ans:

Cost of advertisement (x)	Profit earned (y)	xy	x ²
4	5	16	16
5	6	30	25
3	5	15	9
6	7	42	36
10	7	70	100
$\sum x = 28$	$\sum y = 30$	$\sum xy = 173$	$\sum x^2 = 186$

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$\bar{x} = \frac{28}{5} = 5.6$
 $\bar{y} = \frac{29}{5} = 5.8$

The regression equation is given by $y = a + bx$

Here,

$$b = \frac{\sum xy - n\bar{x}\bar{y}}{\sum x^2 - n(\bar{x})^2}$$

$$= \frac{5 \cdot 173 - 28 \cdot 29}{(28)^2 - (5 \cdot 5.6)^2}$$

$$= \frac{5 \cdot 173 - 28 \cdot 29}{784 - 156.8}$$

$$= \frac{5 \cdot 173 - 28 \cdot 29}{627.2}$$

$$= 0.363$$

and $a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x}$

$$= 5.8 - 0.363 \times 5.6$$

$$= 3.7671$$

So the required regression equation, $y = a + bx = 3.7671 + 0.363x$

(b) $x = 9$ lakh taka

$$y = 3.7671 + 0.363 \times 9$$

$$= 7.0351 \text{ Lakh taka}$$

1	9	7.0351
2	10	7.4011
3	11	7.7671
4	12	8.1331
5	13	8.4991

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Exc: The following table given the age and blood pressure of 10 persons.

Age (x)	56	42	36	47	49	42	72	63	55	60
Blood pressure (y)	147	125	118	128	145	140	155	160	149	150

(a) Determine the regression line of Blood pressure Y on age X.

(b) Estimate the blood pressure of a person whose age is 45 years.

Ans:

Age (x)	Blood Pressure (y)	xy	x ²
56	147	8232	3136
42	125	5250	1764
36	118	4248	1296
47	128	6016	2209
49	145	7105	2401
42	140	5880	1764
72	155	11160	5184
63	160	10080	3969
55	149	8195	3025
60	150	9000	3600
$\Sigma x = 522$	$\Sigma y = 1417$	$\Sigma xy = 75166$	$\Sigma x^2 = 28348$

$\bar{x} = \frac{522}{10} = 52.2$
 $\bar{y} = \frac{1417}{10} = 141.7$

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Ex: The following table gives the relationship between the amount of blood pressure and the amount of blood pressure.

Here, $b = \frac{\sum x_2 y_2 - \sum x_2 \sum y_2}{n(\sum x_2^2) - (\sum x_2)^2}$

Amount of blood pressure (x)	Amount of blood pressure (y)
10	150
12	160
15	170
18	180
20	190
22	200
25	210
28	220
30	230
32	240
35	250
38	260
40	270
42	280
45	290
48	300
50	310
52	320
55	330
58	340
60	350
62	360
65	370
68	380
70	390
72	400
75	410
78	420
80	430
82	440
85	450
88	460
90	470
92	480
95	490
98	500
100	510

10. 28348 - 28348

(a) Determine the regression line of blood pressure Y on age X.

(b) Estimate the blood pressure of a person whose age is 45 years.

$a = 2.4964$

\therefore The regression line of blood pressure, $\hat{y} = 84.802 + 1.09x$

Age (x)	Blood Pressure (y)
30	150
35	160
40	170
45	180
50	190
55	200
60	210
65	220
70	230
75	240
80	250
85	260
90	270
95	280
100	290

Correlation analysis: Correlation is a statistical technique which can show whether and how strongly variables are related. The primary objective of correlation analysis is to measure the strength or degree of linear association of two or more variables. This strength or degree is known as co-efficient of correlation $r = \frac{\sum x_1 y_1}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} = \bar{r}$

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Co-efficient of correlation is denoted by r and defined

by

$$r = \frac{\sum xy - \frac{\sum x \cdot \sum y}{n}}{\sqrt{\left[\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n} \right] \left[\sum y^2 - \frac{(\sum y)^2}{n} \right]}}$$

Ex: Find the co-efficient of linear correlation between the variables x and y presented in the following table.

x	1	3	4	6	8	9	11	14
y	1	2	4	4	5	7	8	9

Ans: To calculate the co-efficient of correlation

x	y	x^2	y^2	xy
1	1	1	1	1
3	2	9	4	6
4	4	16	16	16
6	4	36	16	24
8	5	64	25	40
9	7	81	49	63
11	8	121	64	88
14	9	196	81	126
$\sum x = 56$	$\sum y = 40$	$\sum x^2 = 524$	$\sum y^2 = 256$	$\sum xy = 364$

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force applied

$$\sqrt{\left[\frac{\sum x^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum x}{n} \right)^2 \right] \left[\frac{\sum y^2}{n} - \left(\frac{\sum y}{n} \right)^2 \right]}$$

$$= \sqrt{\left[\frac{364}{8} - \frac{(56)^2}{8} \right] \left[\frac{356}{8} - \frac{(65)^2}{8} \right]}$$

coefficient of correlation

$$= \frac{84}{\sqrt{458.5 - 224} \sqrt{356 - 32}}$$

$$= \frac{84}{\sqrt{234.5} \sqrt{324}}$$

$$= \frac{84}{15.31 \times 18} = 0.31$$

Calculate the co-efficient of correlation from the following data.

x	10	6	9	10	12	13	11
y	9	7	6	9	11	13	8

Ans:

x	y	x ²	y ²	xy
10	9	100	81	90
6	7	36	49	42
9	6	81	36	54
10	9	100	81	90
12	11	144	121	132
13	13	169	169	169
11	8	121	64	88
$\sum x$	$\sum y$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$
71	60	751	510	647

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